

IKKINCHI VA UCHINCHI TIP KLASSIK SOHALAR DEKART KO'PAYTMALARINING BERGMAN YADROSI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada bir jinsli doiraviy matritsaviy sohalarning Bergman yadrolari topish va ularning xossalari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. *Klassik sohalar, Bergman yadrosi, yakobiyani, doiraviy soha, avtomorfizm.*

ANNOTATION

This work is devoted to the search for Bergman kernels of homogeneous circular matrix domains and their properties..

Keywords. *Classical domains, Bergman kernel, Jacobian, circular domain, automorphism.*

Ma'lumki,

$$F_2 = G(B - P_2)(I^{(n)} - \overline{P_2}B)^{-1} \overline{G}^{-1}, \quad (1.1)$$

akslantirish esa, $B_{II}(n)$ ikkinchi tip klassik sohaning, P_2 nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo'ladi, bu yerda $Z \in B_{II}(n)$ va $G \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ matritsalar quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\overline{G}(I^{(n)} - \overline{P_2}P_2)G = I^{(n)}. \quad (1.2)$$

Shuningdek, quyidagi

$$\Phi_3 = A(Z - P_3)(I^{(n)} + \overline{PZ})^{-1} \overline{A}^{-1} \quad (1.3)$$

akslantirish esa, $B_{III}(n)$ ikkinchi tip klassik sohaning, P_3 nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo'ladi, bu yerda $Z \in B_{III}(n)$ va $A \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n \cap n_{\mathbb{B}}^{\mathbb{H}}$ matritsalar quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\overline{A}(I^{(n)} + P_3 \overline{P_3})A\check{y} = I^{(n)}. \quad (1.4)$$

Aytaylik, B sohani $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalarining dekart ko'paytmasi quyidagi ko'rinishida berilgan bo'lsin:

$$B = B_{II}(n) \times B_{III}(n) = \{(B, Z) : B \in B_{II}(n), Z \in B_{III}(n)\},$$

bu yerda,

$$B_{II}(n) = \{B \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n \cap n_{\mathbb{B}}^{\mathbb{H}} : I^{(n)} - B\overline{B} > 0, "B' = B\}.$$

va

$$B_{III}(n) = \{Z \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n \cap n_{\mathbb{B}}^{\mathbb{H}} : I^{(n)} + Z\overline{Z} > 0, "Z\check{y} = -Z\}.$$

Bu B sohaning X ostovi, $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalar X_{II} va X_{III} ostovlari dekart ko'paytmasiga teng bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$X_{II} = \{B \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n \cap n_{\mathbb{B}}^{\mathbb{H}} : B\overline{B} = I^{(n)}, "B' = B\},$$

$$X_{III} = \{Z \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n \cap n_{\mathbb{B}}^{\mathbb{H}} : Z\overline{Z} = I^{(n)}, "Z\check{y} = -Z\}$$

$$X = X_{II} \times X_{III}.$$

U holda yuqoridagi (1.1) va (1.3) munosabatlarga asosan quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli bo'lishini topamiz:

1-tasdiq. Komponentalari mos ravishda (1.2), (1.4) shartlar bilan aniqlanadigan, (1.1) hamda (1.3) ko‘rinishidagi F_2 va F_3 akslantirishlar bilan aniqlanadigan ushbu

$F = (F_2, F_3)$ akslantirish $B = B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohaning

$P = (P_2, P_3) \circ B$ nuqtasini koordinata boshiga akslantiruvchi avtomorfizmi bo‘ladi.

Bremerman teoremasini $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ klassik sohalar dekart ko‘paytmasining Bergman yadrosini topish uchun analogini keltiramiz.

1-teorema. Aytaylik, $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalar $B \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathbb{H}} \times \mathbb{R}^{\mathbb{H}}$ va $Z \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathbb{H}} \times \mathbb{R}^{\mathbb{H}}$ o‘zgaruvchili fazolardagi klassik sohalar va $B = B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ bo‘lsin, u holda quyidagi tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi:

$$K_B(B, Z, \bar{B}, \bar{Z}) = K_{B_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{B}) K_{B_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Z}) \quad (1.5)$$

Isbot. Buning uchun 1-tasdiqga asoslanib, B sohaning $F = (F_2, F_3)$ avtomorfizmi xususiyatlaridan foydalanamiz. Dastlab, (1.1) ko‘rinishdagi F_2 akslantirishni differensiallab ushbu

$$dF_2 = G \Psi B \Psi \left(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 B \right)^{-1} + (B - P_2) d \left(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 B \right)^{-1} \Psi G^{-1},$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Agar $B = P_2$ desak u holda (1.2) shartga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$dF_2 = G \Psi B \Psi \left(I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_2 P_2 \right)^{-1} \Psi G^{-1} = G \Psi B \Psi G^{-1} \quad (1.6)$$

va (1.5) munosabat ushbu

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & K & b_{1n} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & K & b_{2n} \\ K & K & K & K \\ b_{n1} & b_{n2} & K & b_{nn} \end{pmatrix}, G = \begin{pmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & K & g_{1n} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & K & g_{2n} \\ K & K & K & K \\ g_{n1} & g_{n2} & K & g_{nn} \end{pmatrix}, \Phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} h_{11} & h_{12} & K & h_{1n} \\ h_{21} & h_{22} & K & h_{2n} \\ K & K & K & K \\ h_{n1} & h_{n2} & K & h_{nn} \end{pmatrix}.$$

belgilashlar orqali, quyidagi tenglikka ekvivalentdir:

$$dh_{sj} = \prod_{l=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^n g_{si} db_{il} g_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Bu oxirgi tenglikdan $F_2 = (h_{11}, \dots, h_{nn})$ golomorf akslantirish uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'lishi kelib chiqadi:

$$dh_{11} \prod dh_{12} \prod \dots \prod dh_{nn} = \prod_{s,j} \prod_{l=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^n g_{si} db_{il} g_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

U holda $db_{il} = db_{li}$ ekanidan, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} dh_{11} \prod dh_{12} \prod \dots \prod dh_{nn} &= \\ &= \prod_{s,j} (\det G)^s \prod db_{11} \prod db_{12} \dots \prod db_{nn} \prod (\det G)^j, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

tenglik quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} dh_{11} \prod dh_{12} \prod \dots \prod dh_{nn} &= (\det G)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \prod (\det G)^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \prod db_{11} \prod db_{12} \dots \prod db_{nn} = \\ &= J_C(F_2) \prod db_{11} \prod db_{12} \dots \prod db_{nn}, \end{aligned}$$

tenglikka ekvivalent bo'ladi, bu yerda $J_C(F_2)$ - F_2 akslantirishning kompleks yakobiani va u quyidagicha topiladi:

$$J_C(F_2) = (\det G)^{\frac{(n+1)}{2}} \prod (\det G)^{\frac{(n+1)}{2}} = (\det G)^{(n+1)}.$$

Bulardan (1.2) shartga asosan

$$F_2^g = |J_C(F_2)|^2 B^g = \left| (\det G)^{n+1} \right|^2 B^g = \frac{B^g}{\det^{n+1}(I - BB)}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Endi (1.3) ko'rinishdagi Φ_3 akslantirishni differensiallab ushbu

$$dF_3 = A \frac{\check{Y}}{K} Z \prod (I^{(n)} - \bar{P}_3 Z)^{-1} + (Z - P_3) d(I^{(n)} + \bar{P}_3 Z)^{-1} \frac{\check{Y}}{B},$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Agar $Z = P_2$ desak u holda (1.4) shartga asosan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$dF_3 = A \Psi Z \Psi \left(I^{(n)} + \bar{P}_3 P_3 \right)^{-1} \Psi^{-1} = A \Psi Z \Psi'. \quad (1.6)$$

va (1.6) munosabat ushbu

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & z_{12} & \dots & z_{1n} \\ z_{21} & 0 & \dots & z_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ z_{n1} & z_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 0 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Phi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} v_{11} & v_{12} & \dots & v_{1n} \\ v_{21} & v_{22} & \dots & v_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ v_{n1} & v_{n2} & \dots & v_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

belgilashlar orqali quyidagi tenglikka ekvivalentdir:

$$dv_{sj} = \prod_{l=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^n a_{si} dz_{il} a_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Bu oxirgi tenglikdan $F_3 = (v_{11}, \dots, v_{nn})$ golomorf akslantirish uchun quyidagi tenglik o‘rinli bo‘lishi kelib chiqadi:

$$dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} = \prod_{s,j} \prod_{l=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^n a_{si} dz_{il} a_{lj}, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

U holda $dz_{il} = -dz_{li}$ ekanidan, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} &= \\ &= \prod_{s,j} (\det A)^s \Psi z_{11} \wedge \dots \wedge \Psi z_{nn} \Psi' (\det A')^j, s = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned}$$

tenglik quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} &= (\det A)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \Psi (\det A')^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \Psi z_{11} \wedge \dots \wedge \Psi z_{nn} = \\ &= J_C(F_3) \Psi z_{11} \wedge \dots \wedge \Psi z_{nn}, \end{aligned}$$

tenglikka ekvivalent bo'ldi, bu erda $J_C(F_3)$ - Φ_3 akslantirishning kompleks yakobiani va u quyidagicha topiladi:

$$J_C(F_3) = (\det A)^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} \overline{(\det A')}^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} = (\det A')^{(n-1)}.$$

Bulardan (1.4) shartga asosan

$$K_3 = |J_C(F_3)|^2 Z = \left| (\det A)^{n-1} \right|^2 Z = \frac{Z}{\det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Shunday qilib, yuqoridagi mulohazalarimizga ko'ra $F = (h_{11}, \dots, h_{nn}, v_{11}, \dots, v_{nn})$

akslantirish uchun quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} dh_{11} \wedge dh_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dh_{nn} \wedge dv_{11} \wedge dv_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dv_{nn} = \\ = J_C(F_2) db_{11} \wedge db_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge db_{nn} J_C(F_3) dz_{11} \wedge dz_{12} \wedge \dots \wedge dz_{nn} \end{aligned}$$

tenglik bajarilishi va uning haqiqiy yakobiani ushbu

$$J_R(F) = \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B}) \det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})}$$

tenglik bilan topilishi kelib chiqadi. Ma'lumki, $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalaring

Bergman yadrolari quyidagi ko'rinishda topiladi:

$$K_{B_{II}}(n)(b, \bar{b}) = \frac{1}{V(B_{II}(n))} \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I^{(n)} - B\bar{B})},$$

$$K_{B_{III}}(n)(z, \bar{z}) = \frac{1}{V(B_{III}(n))} \frac{1}{\det^{n-1}(I^{(n)} + Z\bar{Z})},$$

bu yerda, $V(B_{II}(n))$ va $V(B_{III}(n))$ miqdorlar mos ravishda $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalarning hajmlari. Demak, ushbu

$$\begin{aligned}
K_B(B, Z, \bar{B}, \bar{Z}) &= \frac{1}{\det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B})\det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})} = \\
&= \frac{1}{V(B_{II}(n))\det^{n+1}(I - B\bar{B})} \frac{1}{V(B_{III}(n))\det^{n-1}(I + Z\bar{Z})} = \\
&= K_{B_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{B}) K_{B_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Z}).
\end{aligned}$$

munosabatlar o‘rinli bo‘lishi kelib chiqadi. *Teorema isbot bo‘ldi.*

Bu 1-teoremadan ushbu natija kelib chiqadi.

1-natija. Aytaylik, $B_{II}(n)$ va $B_{III}(n)$ sohalar $B \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n$ va $Z \in C_{\mathbb{H}}^n$ o‘zgaruvchili fazolardagi klassik sohalar va $B = B_{II}(n) \cup B_{III}(n)$ bo‘lsin, u holda quyidagi tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi:

$$K_B(B, Z, \bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = K_{B_{II}(n)}(B, \bar{Y}) K_{B_{III}(n)}(Z, \bar{Z}) \quad (1.7)$$

bu yerda, $B, Y \in B_{II}(n), Z, Z \in B_{III}(n)$.

B sohada dm o‘lchov bo‘yicha kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalar fazosini $L^2(B)$ bilan, $H^2(B)$ bilan esa $L^2(B)$ sinfga golomorf davom qiluvchi uning qism fazoni belgilaymiz. 1-natijadan va Zommer-Mering teoremasiga asosan quyidagi teorema o‘rinli bo‘lishi kelib chiqadi.

2-teorema. Ixtiyoriy $f \in H^2(B)$ funksiyalar uchun

$$f(B, Z) = \int_B f(Y, \bar{Z}) K_B(B, Z, \bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) dm, \quad (Y, \bar{Z}) \in B$$

Bergman-Bremermann integral formulasi o‘rinli.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

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